

**The Journal of the Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies, Faculty of Arts**
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

LEAD CITY JOURNAL OF RELIGIONS AND INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

(ISSN 3043-4416)

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Herdsmen Attacks and Its Economic Consequences in Apa Local Government of Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research accentuated herdsmen's attacks and the economic consequences in Apa Local Government Area of Benue State. The work aimed at examining these attacks so as to ascertain their economic imports on the people and to proffer solutions towards resolving farmers/herdsmen conflicts. Fulani herdsmen attacks had brought untold hardships to the people of Nigeria, Benue, and Apa Local Government in particular. These attacks have resulted in the destruction of human lives and property, farm lands and crops, displacement of people and loss of means of livelihood. The paper used descriptive and analytical methods, and the services of primary and secondary sources of data collection and analysis, to address the issues raised. The findings revealed that herdsmen/farmer conflicts usually occur due to: struggle for grazing fields, farmers obstruction to the grazing route, herdsmen leading their cattle to destroying farmlands and crops, herders' resistance with superiors firearms, pollution of village stream water, and incessant raping and kidnapping for ransom. All these have led to constant clashes between the two opposing parties, with recurrent damages on both sides. It is very important that efforts towards ending these clashes by all parties, should be on top gear. In other to achieve this, the work recommended that herders and farmers should learn to be law-abiding, embrace peace and to shun violence. Dialogue for peaceful coexistence should be encouraged, while the government should establish ranching methods of rearing animals and banish pastoral methods, which have become obsolete today.

Keywords: **Herdsmen, attacks, economy, Apa Local Government of Benue State**

Introduction

Fulani herdsmen and farmers' clashes and attacks have become a common worrisome phenomenon in the contemporary society, as this poses both economic and security threat. Apart from Boko Haram, one recurrent security challenge that confronts many states in the country is the challenge of Fulani herdsmen. These attacks on several communities in Nigeria have been on the increase in recent times (Akevi, 2016). Durojaiye (2014), noted that, "there have been escalations of reported attacks by Fulani herdsmen who brutally kill natives of the invaded farming communities including women and children in various states across the country." In view of this, the Global Terrorism Index (GTI) (2015, p. 43) reported that Fulani herdsmen are believed to have killed at least 1, 229 people in Nigeria in 2014. This view was collaborated by the International Crisis Group (ICG) in (2018). It was noted that in the first half of 2018, more than 1,300 Nigerians perished in violence involving herdsmen and farmers. The worst affected states include: Benue, Nassarawa, Plateau, Taraba, Kaduna, Adamawa, Zamfara, Oyo, Imo, Cross River, Abia, Ebonyi and Rivers. Fulani herdsmen normally attack their target communities at the time they are most susceptible, such as mid-night, or prayer days, when they are in their churches; incessantly killing people with sophisticated weapons, looting properties and burning houses (Durojaiye, 2014).

The above painted scenario is a true reflection of what happens in Apa Local Government Area of Benue State. Here, Fulani herdsmen attacks, have been a recurrent decimal, with little or no provocation, leading to loss of lives and properties and the destruction of valuable government and private properties in the communities (International Crisis Group, 2018). Ofuoku & Isife (2016) investigated the causes of conflicts between farmers and Fulani herdsmen. They noted that it as a result of competition over available resources, especially land and water, which are the major sources of livelihoods and lifestyles of these groups. Other factors adduced are, religious supremacy and the Judaist advancement of Islam in Christian-dominated areas like Benue State and its communities. Citing Ingawa et al (1999), Aniche, & Ngwu (n.d, p.7) stressed that, "the key underlying causes of herdsmen and farmers conflicts in Nigeria include the changing resources access rights, whereby traditional access rights to communal grazing and water resources are being obstructed by the individual tenureship of arable

farmers.” This is particularly severe on the traditional trek routes, which become favorite cropping sites because of their better soil fertility resulting from the concentration of animal manure from the trekking herds in these areas, which makes prevention on animals straying in the crop plots difficult (Aniche & Ngwu, n.d).

Herdsmen attacks have great negative impacts on families, villages, communities, educational systems, and religious institutions, bringing about socio-religious, economic and security challenges on daily basis. Nomadic herders have assumed a terrorist position, kidnapping, harassing, killing, maiming, raping, and causing mass casualties to the loss of lives and properties. The Fulani herders usually equipped with sophisticated weapons with which they harass and inflict pains on innocent villagers (International Crisis Group, 2018).

Using descriptive and analytical methods, and other sources of data collection, the work studied the economic effects of Fulani herdsmen attacks on Apa Local Government Area of Benue State. The devastation caused by herdsmen attacks, enablers of herdsmen attacks, and the results of herdsmen attacks on the affected communities, economic damage, and ways of resolving herdsmen attacks, were all taken into considerations in this research. The findings of this work will benefit Apa Local Government Area of Benue State, religious and educational institutions, policymakers in Nigeria and the world at large.

Understanding Herdsmen and their Operations

Olawale (2022, p. 210) noted that “herdsmen commonly involve individuals or groups engaged in the pastoral care and management of livestock, especially cattle, sheep, and goats.” In so many parts of Africa, North Africa, and West Africa, herdsmen are primarily involved in nomadic or semi-nomadic livestock rearing, always moving their animals in search of green pasture and water. This practice, known as pastoralists, has deep cultural, economic, and social roots, especially among certain ethnic groups. In Nigeria, for instance, the Fulani ethnic group is commonly known for its long-standing shepherd or pastoralist’s tradition (Olawale, 2022). Agada & Bature (2023), affirmed that “it is a cultural oriented practice. It is not just merely for economic purpose, but is intertwined with their identity and social structure.” Herdsmen groups always have social norms, conflict resolution mechanisms, and cultural rites that revolve around herding.

On economic and food security, Reynolds (2014) observed that “herdsmen contribute significantly to the agricultural sector by providing meat, milk, hides, and other animal products. They also create employment and play a role in trade networks and economic growth in society.” The rearing of livestock in Nigeria has contributed immensely to economic growth and the availability of meat in the market. However, in recent years, it has been noted that Fulani herdsmen have been at the center of crises, to be specific, Nigeria in particular, where competition over land and resources has intensified clashes between herders, farmers, and hosting communities. This situation is compounded by environmental factors such as desertification and climate change, lack of stream water, and green grass, which reduce available pasture. Thus, when herdsmen attempt to impose the livestock on farmers’ crops, and farmland deliberately, this generates tension and conflict.

The situation has heightened fears and mistrust between communities, as herdsmen attacks are often marked by violence, destruction of property, and loss of life. The height of herdsmen attacks has led to the death of many innocent persons, loss of livelihood, jobs, mass displacement of people, overcrowding in urban areas, overdependence, as well as an increase in the high rate of crime and other social vices erupting in the society (Abolaji & Ahmed, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

The theories that framed this research are that of frustration-aggression theory of Dolard, Doob, Mileer, Mowrer, and Sears, propounded in 1939 and conflict theory of Karl Marx in 1841. The frustration-aggression theory best describes the menace of Fulani herdsmen in Nigeria. This theory which was also known as frustration-aggression-displacement theory was developed by John Dollard and his associates in 1939. Elson (2018) described the theory as frustration-aggression hypothesis. The theory was expanded and modified by Yate in 1962 and Berkowitz in 1963, which draws mainly from psychological basis of motivation and behaviour (Ogege, 2015).

The theoretical framework explains the violent behavioural pertain which is caused by the inability of individuals to fulfill human needs. According to the theorists, the main cause of human capacity for violence is frustration aggression mechanism. This means unfulfilled expectations create relative deprivation gap between expectation and

capabilities and can lead to violence or conflict. In other words, when someone or group of people have the perception of their ability or right to something (goal), if prevented from attaining such goals the result is frustration which will in turn generate aggressive behaviour that will snowball to violence (Ojo, 2014). Citing Dollard et al. (1939), Arie (2023, p. 446) noted that, “frustration produces instigation to aggression.”

The theory ranks among the most seminal and prominent theories in research on aggression. It is relevant for this research because, the herdsmen and farmers, when frustrated, will eventually lead to aggression, and aggression will result in herders attacking the host communities due to the destruction of farm crops and fields for cultivation by herders. Frustration from farmers and villagers and the host communities will lead to aggression and these will result in attacks and killings, destruction of lives and property, and displacement of people. The Fulani herders usually feel frustrated when encroachment of grazing fields or tracks by farmers occurs, in other words, by banning them from having access to water for their cattle, stealing their cattle or sheep, or poisoning the grass for cattle, leading to the loss of livestock, lead to frustration. The above-mentioned issues often cause frustration and aggression, which nurture violence either by herdsmen or farmers in retaliation or attacks. This is usually the case in Apa Local Government Area of Benue State.

On the other hand, the conflict theory as propounded by the German philosopher Karl Marx (1818-1883), is a social theory that discusses the ensuing conflict between the rich and the poor in the society to control scarce resources. Karl Marx stated that conflict will continue to persist in society due to the limited resources and people’s struggle to control and dominate. Conflict is viewed as a process of competition, struggle, and dominance. Conflict theory understands society as being made up of individuals competing for scarce resource which is at the heart of all social relationships. Competition rather than consensus is characteristics of human relationships. Broader social structures and organizations reflect the competition for resources and the inherent inequality competition entails some people and organizations have more resources (power and influence) and use those resources to maintain their positions of power in the society. Conflict between the oppressors and the oppressed exists in every part of society.

The herdsmen are full of oppression, and farmers are filled with oppression. The herders take the position of oppressors or farmers, and the host communities become the oppressed. Farmers and herders struggle to determine who controls the limited resources, and resistance from any side will end in violence. This is the case in Apa L.G.A., where herders are trying to gain control, forcing themselves on host communities to have grazing fields, water for their animals, and encroachment of herders in reserve land for grazing. Fulani herders also march their animals to destroy farms crops, pollution of available stream waters, and raping of women on the farm, among others, which have triggered persistent conflict resulting in the loss of human lives, livestock, and properties and the displacement of people.

Conflict theory of Karl Marx, like the frustration- aggression theory, is useful in this work in all respects. This is because the society today, is still full of inequalities. The struggle for scarce resources continue to lead to violence among people. This is a true picture of what is happening in Apa today.

Herdsmen and Farmers Conflict in Apa Local Government Area

Adisa & Adegunle (2010) noted that, “the clashes between herdsmen and farmers in Nigeria and other regions have generated significant research interest, particularly regarding the causes, impacts, and resolutions of these conflicts.” The herdsmen and farmers conflicts are primarily over land and resources, with herders seeking grazing grounds while farmers require land for cultivation. Factors like climate change, population growth and changing land policies have intensified these clashes (Alhassan, 2013). Fulani herdsmen encroaching on farmlands usually, lead to the destruction crops and escalating tensions. Farmers, in response, do take defensive measures to protect their livelihoods, leading to violent clashes. Ethnic and religious identities further complicate these disputes, particularly in regions like Nigeria’s Middle Belt, Benue State, and Apa Local Government Areas, where herders are often Muslim Fulani and farmers are generally Christians. This explains the economic impact of the conflicts, highlighting the severe consequences for agricultural productivity and the social disruption in affected communities. Adisa (2012) stressed that land tenure system ownership was regarded as a cause of the conflicts. In most areas in

Nigeria, farmers are regarded as those that own the land, and therefore determine how it is used, while the herdsmen are regarded as the landless group who do not own land to use and settle on.

According to A. Omia (personal communication, October, 30, 2024), herdsmen often deliberately lead their livestock to destroy farm crops and intentionally undermine traditional authority, all in an attempt to Islamize Benue and Nigeria. Herdsmen and farmers clashes cause more harm to herders and farmers; the end product is always loss of lives and properties, especially on the side of farmers and host communities.

Government policies according to Hoffman et al. (2008) is said to be one of the major causes of herdsmen/farmers conflicts. For instance, conflict do occur as the size of the existing reserve shrinks due to encroachment and government approved expansion of farmlands. This leads to the conversion of water points and stock routes into farmlands. Bello (2013, pp.129-139) enumerated the other causes of herdsmen/farmers conflicts to be: (1) destruction of crops by cattle and other property (reservoirs, irrigational facilities and infrastructure) by the herdsmen themselves. (2) burning of range lands, fadama and blockage of stock routes and water points by crop encroachment are important direct reasons cited by the herdsmen. (3) increasing rate of cattle theft which is often accompanied by violence. (4) antagonistic perception and beliefs among farmers and herdsmen compound conflict situation, especially due to failing institutions and fierce competition for resources.

Constant attacks by suspected Fulani herdsmen on communities in Apa Local Government Area of Benue State have left multiple casualties and forced many residents to flee their homes. In early May 2024, herdsmen launched coordinated assaults on several villages, including Ikobi, Edikwu-Olekle, Opaha, and Obinda-Odugbo, leading to numerous deaths, injuries, and significant property destruction. The violence also extended to the nearby Agatu Local Government Area, where the situation remains dire with ongoing attacks (Alhassan, 2013). The assaults have devastated the local population, with homes, farmland, and essential infrastructure being destroyed. Survivors reported that the attackers always fire sporadically and laid siege to villages for hours, displacing the entire communities. Local youth usually make efforts to repel the attackers, but the scale and frequency of the violence always take many unawares and overwhelmed.

Local leaders, such as those from the Apa Development Association, have decried the attacks, emphasizing the suffering of women and children, who have been particularly vulnerable. The state representative for Apa, lamented the displacement of nearly 95% of the area's population, and several communities now lie abandoned (D. Umoru, personal communication, October, 30, 2024). Despite repeated calls for intervention, the attacks have continued unabated, causing widespread fear and devastation.

Consequences of Herdsmen Attacks on Economic Development in Apa

The conflicts between farmers and Fulani herdsmen in Apa have been the major cause of increasing violence and general insecurity in all ramifications. Herdsmen have killed so many people in different parts of Nigeria, razing homes and farmlands and sending thousands fleeing to nowhere. This has far reaching socio-economic effects on the people (Ofuoku & Isife, 2010).

Okeke (2015 p. 145), decried the impact of these attacks when and where they occur. He noted that, "the social impact is usually profound, with disruptions to community life, reduced inter-group trust, and displacement of populations." Economically, these conflicts have caused losses in agricultural output, with communities incurring heavy economic burdens due to destroyed farmlands and loss of cattle. Many scholars argue that the conflicts exacerbate poverty in affected regions and have led to food insecurity. This explores how ethnic and religious dynamics shape the herdsmen and farmers' clashes, analyzing the complex identity issues that complicate the conflict.

The impact of herdsmen attacks on economic development has been a growing concern and worry, especially in the agrarian regions where these conflicts are most intense, particularly in Apa Local Government Area, Benue State. The attacks often lead to the displacement of farming communities, which disrupts agricultural productivity and contributes to food insecurity. Additionally, there is a decline in local investments as the heightened insecurity deters potential investors, further slowing economic growth in affected regions. According to a study conducted by Aliyu (2018, p. 245), "the repeated attacks reduce household incomes and contribute to a rise in poverty levels among rural populations, as

families lose their primary sources of livelihood, such as cattle and crop farms.”

The economic effects extend beyond direct losses to agricultural output. Odoh & Chigozie (2012), highlighted that infrastructure is often damaged during attacks, leading to increased public spending on rebuilding efforts rather than developmental projects. The tourism industry in some areas is also affected, as insecurity discourages both domestic and foreign visitors. Consequently, the cumulative effect of these disruptions is a decline in regional GDP and overall economic stagnation, which is difficult to reverse, given the ongoing nature of these conflicts. Truly speaking, Fulani herdsmen perpetual clashing with farmers has brought untold hardship, food scarcity, insecurity, and underdevelopment across the Apa and the entire Benue State, not excluding Nigeria, as observed by O. Ogbole & S. Omafufu, (personal communication, September, 17, 2024).

Okopi, & Omogbehin (2024, p. 194) affirmed that, “the consequences of herdsmen attacks on economic development in Nigeria are far-reaching, affecting agriculture, infrastructure, trade, and investment opportunities.” These violent conflicts disrupt the productivity of key economic sectors and destabilize rural economies, which are primarily agricultural.

Areas affected by herdsmen attacks like Apa, often experience a significant reduction in investment. Investors shy away from high-risk areas, reducing development in key industries. Note that the continued insecurity discourages both local and foreign investments, particularly in agriculture and tourism, stalling economic development. In line with the above statement, A. Sani (personal communication, November, 1, 2024) observed that, “Fulani herdsmen entered their villages and killed people, displacing people from their ancestral land. This killing and maiming of farmers by herdsmen have discouraged many investors from investing in agriculture in Apa Local Government Area, communities, and farmland deserted for fear of being attacked by herdsmen.”

Herdsmen attacks lead to the destruction of infrastructure, including roads, storage facilities, and marketplaces. The government incurs increased security expenses, which diverts resources from essential development projects. According to Y. Audu (personal communication, October, 10, 2024), “the economic burden of these attacks extends to heightened government spending on security operations, undermining

funds available for economic growth initiatives.” As noted by O. Edo (personal communication, September, 17, 2024), “Fulani herdsmen had rendered many villages in Apa local government to a desert or ghost community. With many houses, mansions, churches, and school buildings destroyed. Threats and fears have become the other of the day. The raiders’ herdsmen wreak havoc on broad daylight unchallenged and go scorch-free. Places like Ochumekwu, Ugbobi, and Ijaha, among other villages, have been completely pulled down.”

The plethora of economic damage by herdsmen attack in Apa, cannot be exhausted within the scope of this paper. The effects are colossal, affecting not just the local communities but the entire nation by extension. To rebuild the damage done and trauma caused to the people, it will take a decisive action of all stake holders. But stopping the continuation of the mayhem, will be a better step in the right direction. This will dominate the discussion in what follows.

Resolving Herdsmen and Farmers Conflict in Nigeria

According to Premium Times (2018) report, “there is need to develop a new policy framework on the farmers-pastoralists crisis that is both comprehensive and mutually beneficial to both groups.” To this end, there must be a consultative process that listens to the concerns of all stakeholders in developing the new framework, so that the outcome would have national ownership. Pastoralism is not sustainable in Nigeria over the long term due to the high population growth rate, expansion of farming and loss of pasture and cattle routes. At the same time, pastoralism cannot end or be prohibited in the short term, as there are strong cultural and political economy reasons for its existence. A comprehensive approach to address the growing crisis associated with violence affecting pastoralism and farmers in Nigeria is necessary (Premium Times, 2018).

According to Emmanuel & Bamidele (2020), the importance of resolving herders/farmers’ conflict for optimal socio-economic attainment, cannot be overemphasized. On this note, the researchers have proffered few key strategies to nipping the menace in the bud. There is need to improving land use policies and demarcation. Establishing clear land boundaries for agricultural and grazing purposes will reduce disputes over land usage. Improved policies on land demarcation, particularly for designated grazing routes, could alleviate encroachment issues that lead

to conflict. Furthermore, A. Gowon (personal communication, October, 5, 2024) said, “it is good to demarcate boundaries for herdsmen and farmers to avoid future clashes and tension.”

Encouraging dialogue between herdsmen and farming communities through peace committees will foster better understanding and promote conflict resolution. Many of those interviewed advocated for traditional leaders and community representatives as mediators to manage local conflicts (B. Ojo, personal communication, November, 1, 2024).

According to I. Amodu (personal communication, November, 2, 2024), it is imperative to set up early warning systems that monitor potential conflicts as this will go a long way in assisting authorities respond before issues escalate. These systems often involve reporting mechanisms within communities to alert local law enforcement agents to rising tensions.

Establishing government-sponsored grazing reserves will reduce the need for nomadic herdsmen to move through farming territories. Such reserves ensure controlled movement and provide resources needed for sustainable herding practices (Onah, 2020). However, of all the solutions proffered, that of ranching seems to be the best option for the herdsmen and the nation as a whole. A practice as old as civilisation, this requires the herdsmen to remain in a particular environment which is then given the necessary infrastructural facelifts and security, buyers can come to these ranches to purchase their cows, while the herdsmen can benefit from the provision of healthcare services and educational services (Premium Times, 2018).

Finally, educating both herders and farmers on sustainable practices will help in managing the available land more effectively. Training programmes for both groups on modern agricultural practices will definitely, prevent land degradation and reduce competition over resource. This will go a long way in addressing the menace of Fulani herdsmen in Apa and the entire nation (Onah, 2020).

Conclusion

The clashes between Fulani herdsmen and farmers in Apa of Benue State, have been a thing of concern, with profound social, economic, and religious impacts. The root causes of these conflicts are often linked to resource scarcity, competition over land use, and broader socio-political dynamics. Farmers depend on land for crop cultivation, while herdsmen

rely on land for grazing areas, leading to disputes that usually escalate into violence.

The consequences of these clashes include the loss of lives, displacement of communities, destruction of property, and a breakdown of trust among local populations. Economically, these conflicts disrupt agricultural productivity and food security, exacerbating poverty in affected communities. Socially, they strain communal relationships, hinder social gatherings, and impact religious worship practices, especially in conflict-prone areas. This research concludes that Fulani herdsmen and farmers should embrace dialogue, peace, ranching methods, and tolerance for peaceful coexistence.

Recommendations

To address herdsmen/farmers' conflicts in Apa, the work recommends as follows:

1. That policies which clearly define and regulate land use and grazing areas, be implemented. This will go a long way to help prevent land conflicts. Setting up designated grazing reserves or ranches, as well as implementing stricter land tenure policies, is very key towards solution.
2. Encouraging dialogue between community leaders, herdsmen, and farmers will foster understanding and peaceful coexistence. Traditional conflict resolution methods often hold cultural significance and will be more readily accepted by communities than state interventions in most cases.
3. Developing livelihood programs for both farmers and herdsmen, such as education on sustainable farming and herding practices, will reduce the need for migratory practices that usually lead to clashes.
4. Establishment of effective security systems and early warning mechanisms in vulnerable areas is capable of detecting and responding to potential conflicts before they escalate. This is very key to ending constant conflicts between the opposing parties.
5. Relevant agencies should address environmental issues such as climate change and desertification, which drive herdsmen southward in search of pastures. This should be able to reduce pressure on resources and mitigate the causes of migration that lead to conflicts. The importance of tolerance and peaceful

coexistence by both herdsmen and farmers and the host communities, cannot be overemphasized.

References

- Abolaji, J. A. & Ahmed, O. M. (2015). "Herdsmen's /Farmers' Conflicts and Sustainable National Development in Nigeria." *The Ethiopian Journal of Social Sciences Volume 8, Number 1*, [ajol-file-journals-709-article](#). Retrieved on 18th Nov., 2024.
- Adisa, R. (2012). *Land use conflict between farmers and Herdsmen- implications for agricultural Extension and rural development*. Ilorin: Univ. of Ilorin.
- Adisa, R.S., & Adekunle, O.A (2010). "Farmers-Herdsmen Conflicts: A factor Analysis of Socio-Economic Conflict Variables among Crop Farmers in Nigeria." *Journal of Human Ecology*, 30, 1-9.
- Agada & Bature (2023). "The Journal of African Conflicts and Peace Studies." *Scholar Commons, University of South Florida*.
<https://www.academia.edu/journal>. Retrieved on 18th Nov., 2024.
- Akevi, J. (2016). "Addressing the scourge of Fulani herdsmen in Benue State." *Eagle Reporters Journal*, 1 (2)
- Alhassan, U. B. (2013). *Herdsmen and Farmers Conflicts in the North Eastern Nigeria: Causes, Repercussions and Resolutions*. Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies. www.researchgate.net/publication. Retrieved on 19th Nov., 2024.
- Aliyu M. K. (2018). "Assessment of the Effects of Farmers- Herdsmen Conflicts on National Integration in Nigeria." www.researchgate.net/publication. Retrieved on 19th Nov., 2024.
- Aniche, A. N & Ngwu, U.L (n.d). "Herdsmen and farmers conflicts in Nigeria: the implications for social work practice." Department of Sociology and Psychology Godfrey Okoye University, Enugu.
- Arie, W. K., & Molly, E. et al. (2024). "Frustration –Aggression Hypothesis Reconsidered: The Role of Significance quest. Research Article. Onlinelibrary.wiley.com. retrieved on 19th Nov., 2024.
- Arinze, I. (2022) "Resolving the herdsmen issue in Nigeria." retrieved on 23, November, 2024 from <https://thenationonlineng.net/resolving-the-herdsmen-issue-in-nigeria/>
- Bello, A. (2013). "Herdsmen and farmers conflicts in North Eastern Nigeria: causes, repercussions and resolutions." MCSER-CEMASSapienza, Univ. of Rome, in *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(5)
- Dollard, J. et al. (1939). "The Frustration and Aggression Hypothesis." *The Free Encyclopedia*, Article. Enwikipedia.org. Retrieved on 18th Nov., 2024.

- Durojaiye, R. (2014 July, 8). "Challenges of Fulani herdsmen." Editorial, *Daily Independence*.
- Emmanuel, I. O. & Bamidele, E. O. (2020). "Resolving Herdsmen Attacks." *ajol-file-journals-310-article*.
- Global Terrorism Index (2015). "Measuring and understanding the impact of terrorism. Institute for Economics and Peace." Retrieved November 17, 2016 from <https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/194968/Global-terrorism-index-2015.pdf>
- Hoffman, I, Umar, B & Tukur, H (2008). "Crisis and Cooperation over control and management of Zamfara Reserve, Nigeria." In Gefu, J.O Clement, B.I.A and Maisamari, B (Eds). *The future of trans-humane pastoralism in West and Central Africa: Strategies, dynamics, conflicts and intervention*, Shika-zaria: National Animal Production Research Institute.
- Iheanacho, E.N. (2017). "The menace of Fulani herdsmen in Nigeria: A threat to national security." *South East Political Science Review*, Vol.1 No.1, Imo State University, Owerri.
- Ingawa, S. A., Ega, A & Erhabor, P. (1999). *Farmer -Pastoralist conflict in core states of the National Fadama Project*. Abuja: FACU
- International Crisis Group (2018). "Report on Herdsmen Attacks." www.crisisgroup.org. Retrieved on 18th Nov., 2024.
- Karl, M. (1818). "What is Conflict Theory?" www.investopedia.com. Retrieved on 19th Nov., 2024.
- Odo S.I. & Chigozie, C.F. (2012). "Climate Change and Conflict in Nigeria: A Theoretical and Empirical Examination of the Worsening Incidence of Conflict between Fulani Herdsmen and Farmers in Northern Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business Management Review*, 2, 110-124. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0002246>.
- Ofu, O.U. (2015). "The Cattle are "Ghanaians" but the Herders are Strangers." *African Studies quarterly*. <https://asq.africa.ufi>. Edu.uploads. 2024. Retrieved on 19th Nov., 2024.
- Ofuoku, A. & Isife, B. (2010). Causes, effects and resolution of farmers – nomadic cattle herders conflict in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 1, 2.
- Ofuoku, A. & Isife, B. (2016). "The Causes of Conflicts between Farmers and Fulani Herdsmen." <https://ir.nilds.gov.ng.res.pdf>. Retrieved on 18th Nov., 2024.
- Ogege, S. O. (2013). "Insecurity and Sustainable Development: The Boko Haram Debacle in Nigeria." *American International Journal of Social Sciences*, 4 (11).

- Ojo, O. V. (2011). "The Turbulent Election History: An Appraisal of Precipitation Factors in Nigeria." *International Journal of Politics and Good Governance*, 5 (52).
- Okopi, O. & Omogbehin, E. L. (2024). "Farmers-Herders Rivalry and its Implications for Food Security and Household income in Nigeria: Interrogation the Trending Issues." *Journal of Policy and Development Studies (JPDS)*. Vol. 16. Ajol- file- journals.724. Article.
- Olawale (2022). "Understanding Herdsmen and their Operations." <https://www.researchgate.net>. Retrieved on 18th Nov., 2024. *Trending Issues. Journal of Policy and Development Studies (JPDS)* Vol. 16. P.194. ajol- file-journals-724. Article.
- Reynolds, L. P. (2024). "Importance of Animals in Agricultural Sustainability and food-Security." [Pmc.ncbi.nlm.gov/articles](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.gov/articles). Retrieved on 18th Nov., 2024.